

RehabMove 2018: ANALYSIS OF GROUND REACTION FORCES BY FOREARM CRUTCHES DURING INSTEP KICK IN AMPUTEE FOOTBALL

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PURPOSE: The purpose of this study was to compare the difference in ground reaction forces (GRF) generated by forearm crutches during instep kick of amputee football players between experienced players and beginners.

METHODS: 12 collegiate students without amputation of their leg participated in this study as the subjects simulated amputee. They were composed of 6 experienced players (height: 170.9 ± 3.4 cm, weight: 66.6 ± 9.9 kg, experience period: 1.8 ± 1.1 years) and 6 beginners (height: 170.0 ± 2.1 cm, weight: 62.8 ± 7.2 kg). They performed a maximal instep kick by using crutches instead of the support leg. The peak vertical components of GRF (vGRF; superior: +) and anteroposterior components of GRF (apGRF; posterior: +) in the kicking leg side (KLS) and the non-kicking leg side (NKLS) generated by crutches were collected by eight force plates.

RESULTS: In the experienced players, the peak vGRF of NKLS (8.2 ± 1.0 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (7.1 ± 1.2 N/kg; $p < 0.05$), and the peak apGRF of NKLS (2.7 ± 0.5 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (1.0 ± 0.4 N/kg; $p < 0.05$). In the beginners, the peak vGRF of NKLS (6.7 ± 1.3 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (5.0 ± 1.8 N/kg; $p < 0.05$), and the peak apGRF of NKLS (1.3 ± 0.6 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (0.7 ± 0.3 N/kg; $p < 0.05$). The GRF of experienced players in terms of all analyzed items were greater than those of beginners ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION: In amputee football, two crutches replace the support leg, particularly the crutch in NKLS which is the same side of support leg is required similar roles. Because amputee football players also approached the ball from an angle to the direction of ball flight, the vGRF and apGRF were larger in NKLS in both groups. Additionally, vGRF and apGRF of experienced players were greater than those of beginners. In conclusion, generating larger vGRF and apGRF, especially in NKLS, is important to improve the skills of instep kick in amputee football.